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FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF PHENOTYPIC MANIFESTATIONS OF OSTEOARTHRITIS**Aliakhunova M.**

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Abstract

Introduction. Osteoarthritis is a joint disease characterized by cellular stress and degradation of the extracellular matrix, developing with macro- and micro-damage, which activate an abnormal adaptive repair response, including pro-inflammatory immune mechanisms.

Objective. To study the features of the functional state of patients with osteoarthritis by phenotypic signs.

Materials and methods: 80 patients diagnosed with osteoarthritis who are on inpatient treatment for the period from January to April 2022 in the State Institution "RSSPMCTandMR" were examined. Verification of the diagnosis according to ACR diagnostic criteria. The distribution of patients by phenotypes was based on classification criteria.

Results and discussion. According to the results of the study, there was a significant increase in the indicators of fibrinogen and C-reactive protein in all groups, with the exception of patients with a biomechanical phenotype. These changes reflect a close positive relationship ($r=0.252$, $p<0.05$) between the systems of inflammation and coagulation processes.

According to the results of the study, a comparative analysis of the algofunctional Leken index shows the highest value in patients with the CP phenotype, which is explained by the consequence of the altered phenotype of chondrocytes mediated by various autocrine and paracrine signals, which leads to the synthesis of many inflammatory mediators and degradation.

Conclusions: Morphological features of both acute and chronic inflammation are observed and are characterized by recurrent episodes of inflammation. At a late stage, fibrosis may dominate, which is confirmed by an increase in the amount of fibrinogen.

Keywords: osteoarthritis, phenotype, clinical features.

Introduction. Osteoarthritis is a joint disease characterized by cellular stress and degradation of the extracellular matrix, developing with macro- and micro-damage, which activate the restorative abnormal adaptive response, including pro-inflammatory immune mechanisms according to the definition of the International Society for the Study of Osteoarthritis (osteoarthritis research of the International Society of OARSI) in 2015 [1]

Changes that initially develop at the molecular level (abnormal metabolism in the tissues of the joint), subsequently lead to anatomical and physiological disorders (degradation of cartilage, bone remodeling, formation of osteophytes, induction of subclinical inflammation and loss of normal joint function) and the formation of clinical symptoms of the disease.

To date, the etiology and pathogenesis of osteoarthritis have not been fully studied [2], and currently there is no therapy that fully eliminates the disease. It is reported that biochemical changes in the subchondral bone, articular cartilage and synovial membrane play an important role, and changes in extra-cartilaginous

tissues can also serve as primary initiators of the disease preceding cartilage damage.

The process of inflammation and the coagulation system are interconnected and stimulate each other. The coagulation system leads to the activation of thrombin and the formation of fibrin. Fibrinogen refers to acute phase proteins, a protein, a glycoprotein (340 kDa) produced in the liver, consisting of 2 identical subunits, each of which consists of three polypeptide chains AA-, B β - and γ . The normal level of fibrinogen in plasma is from 200 to 400 mg / dl Its plasma level rises with inflammation in response to the action of pro-inflammatory agents, such as IL-6 and other cytokines, by activating gene transcription.

In a recently published systematic review, six phenotypes of OA were identified [3]: 1) the phenotype of minimal joint disease with minor symptoms and discomfort over a long period (modified Julian day); 2) the phenotype of chronic pain (CP); 3) the phenotype of biomechanical disorders (MV); 4) inflammatory phenotype (I); 5) metabolic phenotype (MD); 6) phenotype of altered bone and cartilage metabolism (HCM).

This work is devoted to the study of the features of the functional state of patients with osteoarthritis by phenotypic signs.

Objective. To study the features of the functional state of patients with osteoarthritis by phenotypic signs.

Materials and methods: 80 patients diagnosed with osteoarthritis who are on inpatient treatment for the period from January to April 2022 in the State Institution "RSSPMCTandMR" were examined. Verification of the diagnosis according to ACR diagnostic criteria. The distribution of patients by phenotypes was based on classification criteria: Patients were divided into groups of 20 people according to the following characteristics:

Phenotype Minimally pronounced joint disease (MJD) pain ≤ 3 Kellgren - Lawrence pain ≤ 2 in the last 7 days. Pain assessment on a 10-point scale.

Phenotype Metabolic disorders (MD) presence of diabetes mellitus and BMI ≥ 30 .

The phenotype of Chronic pain (CP) was determined by painful points ≥ 6 located above and below the waist on both sides of the body and axially.

The phenotype is biomechanical (MV) valgus $\geq 2^\circ$ and MOAKS tibial lateral condyle ≤ 1.0 or Varus $\geq 2^\circ$ and MOAKS lateral condyle tibial ≤ 1.0 and MOAKS condyle medial tibial ≥ 2.0 .

Table 1

Clinical characteristics of patients

phenotype	MJD N=20	CP N=20	MB N=20	MD N=20	P
Age	45,03±3,25	65,14±4,78	48,57±2,47	59,24±2,47	<0,05
Gender (female), %	18 (90%)	15 (75%)	17 (85%)	17 (85%)	<0,05
Duration of the disease, years	1,56±0,24	5,27±2,95	3,25±2,14	5,24±0,47	<0,05
The Kellgren – Lawrence X - ray stage, %					
1	0%	25%	15%	75%	<0,05
2	10%	75%	80%	20%	<0,05
3	85%	0%	5%	5%	<0,05
4	5%	0%	0%	0	<0,05
Valgus	10%	10%	5%	75%	<0,05
Varus	15%	25%	25%	35%	<0,05
BMI, kg/m2	30,2±4,4	29,5±5,2	33,5±4	30,6±5,2	<0,05

Functional assessment of joints was carried out according to the algofunctional Leken index. This index includes 12 questions. The maximum number of points is 24. The interpretation of the results is as follows: 0 points – no severity, 1-4 points – mild severity, 5-7 points – moderate severity, 8-10 points – severe severity, 11-13 points – very severe severity, more or equal to 14 points – extremely severe severity.

There was also an assessment of the general condition of the patient by the patient and the doctor according to VAS, expressed in mm.

To assess the functional state of the musculoskeletal system, the passage time of one flight of stairs (10 steps) was measured, in seconds.

Statistical processing was carried out using the MS Excel 2010 program.

Results. In the first group of the phenotype of minimal joint disease with minor symptoms and discomfort for a long period (MJD), the duration of the disease was 1.56±0.24 years. The average age of patients was 45.03±3.25 years. It was less than in patients with other phenotypes (the difference ranged from 0.6 to 1.4 years).

In the second group of patients with the KP phenotype (chronic pain), the average age of patients was 65.14±4.78 years. The duration of the disease is ± 5.27 2.95 years. As can be seen from the table, this group of patients had the highest level of pain, a high Leken index, as well as an assessment of the patient's condition according to VAS ($p < 0,05$).

In the third group, the phenotype of MB (biomechanical disorders) was determined in active patients with a high level of muscle strength, a lower body mass index (BMI), rare and concomitant diseases. The duration of the disease was 3.25±2.14 years. The average age of the patients was 48.57±2.47 years. In addition, despite pronounced radiological changes (90% of patients had stage III or IV Kellgren–Lawrence OA), patients had a low level of pain (Table 2).

In the fourth group, patients with metabolic (MD) phenotypes had an average age of 59.24±2.47 years. The duration of the disease was 5.24±0.47 years. In this group, signs of a more severe inflammatory process in the knee joint prevailed, accompanied by a higher level of C-reactive protein (Table 2).

Table 2

Assessment of the functional state of patients with osteoarthritis by phenotypes

The attribute	MJD N=20	CP N=20	MB N=20	MD N=20	P
Algofunctional Leken index	6,52±0,25	11,56±0,87	3,47±1,24	9,98±2,41	<0,05
Pain intensity according to VAS, mm	36,15±1,25	89,25±3,58	56,27±2,54	68,74±5,26	<0,05
The patient's condition according to VAS, evaluated by a doctor, mm	24,13±2,41	78,04±2,78	47,14±1,45	68,71±1,74	<0,05
The patient's condition according to VAS, assessed by the patient, mm	14,13±1,31	88,04±1,82	64,14±2,47	81,31±2,41	<0,05
Passage time per flight of stairs, sec	15,36±3,58	65,47±25,47	44,25±14,2	35,2±19,25	<0,05
Fibrinogen, mmol/l	422,17±17,63	457,17±25,14	328,19±24,35	652,21±17,21	<0,05
CRP, mg/dl	8,8±4,67	24,17±14,14	8,80±6,56	64,14±11,27	<0,05

According to the results of the study, there was a significant increase in the indicators of fibrinogen and C-reactive protein in all groups, with the exception of patients with a biomechanical phenotype. These changes reflect a close positive relationship ($r=0.252$, $p<0.05$) between the systems of inflammation and coagulation processes.

According to the results of the study, a comparative analysis of the algofunctional Leken index shows the highest value in patients with the CP phenotype, which is explained by the consequence of the altered phenotype of chondrocytes mediated by various autocrine and paracrine signals, which leads to the synthesis of many inflammatory mediators and degradation. For this reason, morphological features of both acute and chronic inflammation are observed and are characterized by recurring episodes of inflammation. At a late stage, fibrosis may dominate, which is confirmed by an increase in the amount of fibrinogen.

Conclusions: morphological features of both acute and chronic inflammation are observed and are characterized by recurrent episodes of inflammation. At a late stage, fibrosis may dominate, which is con-

firmed by an increase in the amount of fibrinogen. Taking into account the data obtained, a personalized approach to assessing the functional state is possible, followed by targeted therapy.

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THE NEUROLOGICAL AND PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL COMPONENTS OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. CAPABILITIES OF PREVENTION AND REHABILITATION

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Abstract

The article provides a theoretical analysis of the causes of arterial hypertension, describes a 3-month observation of the initial stage of the development of arterial hypertension and experiments for one year on non-drug normalization of blood pressure in a group of 33 volunteers. We show that arterial hypertension is associated with spastic conditions of the intervertebral muscles in the lower thoracic spine, which leads to compression of sympathetic nerves that control the transport of water through the kidneys, which in turn upsets the balance of fluid circulation through the circulatory system. Theoretical analysis and experimental data made it possible to formulate a hypothesis about the dominant role of disorders in the activity of the sympathetic part of the nervous system in the development of primary and persistent arterial hypertension. The possibility of prevention of arterial hypertension and non-drug rehabilitation of patients with this disease has been shown.